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7. ZNANSTVENA KONFERENCA Z MEDNARODNO UDELEŽBO ZA ČLOVEKA GRE: PRIHODNOST ZDAJ!

7th SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE WITH INTERNATIONAL PARTICIPATION
ALL ABOUT PEOPLE: FUTURE FIT!

Maribor, 15. - 16. 3. 2019

ZBORNİK POVZETKOV / BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

2. IZDAJA / 2nd EDITION

 Pošta Slovenije

 impol
Aluminium Industry

 ELES
PRENAŠAMO ENERGIJO,
OHRANJAMO RAVNOVESJE.

**7. ZNANSTVENA KONFERENCA Z MEDNARODNO UDELEŽBO
ZA ČLOVEKA GRE: PRIHODNOST ZDAJ! / Zbornik povzetkov**

**7th SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE WITH INTERNATIONAL PARTICIPATION
ALL ABOUT PEOPLE: FUTURE FIT! / Book of Abstracts**

Organizacijski odbor / Organisational board:

dr. Tanja Angleitner Sagadin, dr. Goran Gumze, Anja Bačko, Katarina Pernat, Eneja Kovačič, Špela Ekselenski, Marko Bencak, Uroš Kugl

Znanstveni odbor / Scientific Committee:

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Uredil / Editor: dr. Tanja Angleitner Sagadin

Jezikovni pregled / Linguistic revision: Dominatus d.o.o

Prelom / Pre-press preparation: Tjaša Pogorevc s. p.

Izdaja / Edition: 2. izdaja / 2nd edition

Kraj / Place: Maribor

Založba / Publisher: AMEU – ECM, Alma Mater Press

Za založbo / For the publisher: prof. dr. Ludvik Toplak

Leto izdaje / Year of publishing: 2019

Dostopno na / Available at: <http://press.almamater.si/index.php/amp/catalog/book/12>

CIP - Kataložni zapis o publikaciji
Narodna in univerzitetna knjižnica, Ljubljana
001(082)

ZNANSTVENA konferenca z mednarodno udeležbo Za človeka gre: prihodnost zdaj!
(7 ; 2019 ; Maribor)

Zbornik povzetkov = Book of abstracts / 7. znanstvena konferenca z mednarodno udeležbo Za človeka gre: prihodnost zdaj! = 7th Scientific Conference with International Participaton All About People: Future Fit!, Maribor, 15.-16. 3. 2019 ; [uredila Tanja Angleitner Sagadin]. - 1. izd. = 1st ed. - Maribor : Alma Mater Europaea - ECM, 2019

ISBN 978-961-6966-45-0

1. Dodat. nasl. 2. Angleitner Sagadin, Tanja
299193600

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Marija Jevtić

SYSTEM- PSYCHODYNAMIC APPROACH AND ORGANIZATION'S SUSTAINABILITY

The paper examines the importance of organizational system-psycho-dynamic consulting from the perspective of public health, the importance of "mental health and sustainable development" of organization. Psycho-Social Section of the Group Analytic Society Belgrade, through psychoanalytical and group-analytical approach in understanding psycho-dynamics, and working with institutions, organizations and society, has been studying various methods in the field, in an effort to find a modality to strengthen practical application. By searching more space for action in institutions, organizations and society, it strives to improve institutions' status, and the client's (patient's) status (and health). The paper considers application of system-psycho-dynamic methods working at the individual level and with organization (and citizens), working with clients of various occupations and ages, with different organizations which belong to public/private and health/culture sector. The experience of the setting is varied, (in the consultant's office or the client's workplace), as well as by online communication. The paper also presents connection and significance of this approach to leadership, as well as public health and mental health. Hypothesis that the methodology of system-psycho-dynamic consulting can help an individual, organization and / or civil society, through the experience presented in the paper, is confirmed.

Key words: System-psycho-dynamic organizational consulting, society, organizations, sustainability, mental health

